

Globalized Virus: Taking Us Back to 1990

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The pandemic continues to expand. More than 175 countries and territories have reported cases of COVID-19, the disease caused by the coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2). Case growth has accelerated to more than 1300000 cases and 70,000 deaths as of April 6, 2020. Some geographies have a handful of cases, others with early community transmission have a few hundred, and those with uncontrolled, widespread transmission have tens of thousands. Governments have launched unprecedented public-health and economic responses. The situation evolves by the day.

The Economic Impact

The Coronavirus pandemic is the third shock to the Indian economy in a little over three years. The economy will not escape unhurt. More importantly, households are likely to be hit through loss of jobs and or earnings. The impact of such economic shocks on the labour markets is usually on the young who delay their entry into the labour market in response to a fall in job opportunities. This shows up in a fall in the labour force participation rate. And, quite perversely, leads to a fall in the unemployment rate.

Measuring the unemployment rate during a countrywide lockdown is like measuring water in the ocean. Water, water everywhere / nor any drop to drink. That was from The Rime of the Ancient Mariner by Samuel Taylor Coleridge in 1798. Today, people are stuck in their homes surrounded by empty factories, warehouses, offices and shops everywhere. There are empty job seats everywhere, not any

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to gain. This is in a way leads to the deterioration of household activities. Especially the low-income group get affected the most and the earliest. 21 days lockdown can save the face of government putting responsibility on individuals for the pandemic but how one's need can be satisfied. One's own identity as an earning member in the family is being questioned, that can be (Parenthood, sisterhood, brotherhood and the like).

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1991 marked the great change for Indian economy as well as the lives of Indians. Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization changed us dramatically as the lives of Indians have thrived to the peak of consumerism; globally noted because of our potentiality and educated population. All of these things have come to a standstill with the arrival of the unexpected globalized virus. Though globalization of such virus was unknown to many. There are cases which proves that quite many were aware of such pandemic or the pandemic in the making. This could be termed as a "Third World War" because of the lives we spare and the damage it causes globally and locally.

End of Globalisation?

The coming era will be known for its cold war between countries and much stronger trade wars which can emerge. From a business perspective and economic perspective first thought which can emerge in the minds of the individuals could be this, how can I make use of the situation for growth, purely a profit motive-oriented thinking. At this crucial time only very,

few do have the resources to think in those lines. The collapse of nations and businesses are far beyond any recent crisis.

As a layman in the field of medicine, current knowledge of mine about COVID-19 is inadequate. Even WHO makes conflicting statements and UN is seen nowhere. Every day I am bombarded with 'n' number of opinions and suggestions about COVID-19 but challenging to make out the truth of each of this. I am not sure whether it is thick and thin of globalized village. Though everything seems to be difficult in the coming days, the present scenario opens up a new dimension for all operations in the world.

The interesting fact about the current scenario is that we are back to 1990s; social distancing has put an end to globalization and I see a further drop in coming days. The economic as well as other fields of study grips with fear. This fear induces slowdown, recession and crisis. But this time it is a factual truth because this is fear of death. This fear is the worst fear than all the previous financial as well as economic crisis. None of the economics can escape from this grip. End of this fear is distancing oneself as well as one's own economics from others. Social distancing within an economy and social distancing from economies also; that is the end of globalization.

Brexit and winning of Trump had proved that globalization has reached its peak and is starting to deteriorate. Then the latest trade war between China and America also points fingers to this. The emergence of this virus rang the death bell for globalization. Our lives also have got influenced by globalization and end of this will

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throw many from their livelihood. If this scenario persists widening gap between rich and poor can go higher and higher. The aspect of charity work done by corporates and individuals can turn out to be a compulsory aspect in society; otherwise no one might be ready to do it.

Humanity has experienced Spanish Flu, Plague and Cholera as global epidemic and survived through these difficult times. Then what marked the difference at that point of time is the lack of globalization, which could restrict the spreading. As individuals in the globalized village, anything and everything affects us. It doesn't spare anything even the belief system of the individuals. An infected person will be a stigma to the world. Better to get rid of the same individual for the betterment of society. But the goodness of humanity is not dead. We still see people risking their life for making others better, risking their life to make the world a better place to live.

Concluding Challenge

Historically, pandemics have forced humans to break with the past and imagine their world anew. This one is no different. It is a portal, a gateway between world and the next. We can choose to walk through this with hatred, prejudice and dead ideas, our dead rivers and smoky skies. Or can choose to walk leaving them behind for a better world. Lockdown has shown as a possible coexistence of all facts of life. But how are we going to act out after this seems to be a major risk? Mostly we try our level best to repeat history.